

WASTE-DERIVED NANOCELLULOSE-CHITIN HYBRID MATERIALS WITH TUNABLE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Cellulose and chitin, the most abundant natural polymers in the world, are used in applications ranging from construction and paper to cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and water treatment. Traditionally these polymers have been sourced from finite resources such as forests and crustacean exoskeletons, however they can be sourced more sustainably and at lower cost through waste upcycling. This study investigated nanocellulose-chitin hybrid materials derived from sugarcane by-products; cellulose from bagasse and fungal chitin from mycelial biomass grown on molasses. Hybrid physical properties such as mechanical performance and wettability were then tuned using varying ratios of nanocellulose and *Trametes versicolor* and *Allomyces arbuscular* fungal chitins. The natural polymers were isolated via mild chemical extraction and hot-pressed to produce hybrid materials, utilising more hydrophobic *A. arbuscular* and more hydrophilic *T. versicolor* fungal chitin, reinforced with nanocellulose. The resulting homogenous materials constituted cheap, environmentally sustainable thin films with tunable physical properties, potentially suitable for applications including coatings, membranes and paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is the most abundant organic polymer on Earth, being the structural component of plant cell walls and present in algae and oomycetes [1]. Chitin, which is a derivative of glucose, follows cellulose as the second most abundant natural polymer, occurring in fungal cell walls, arthropod exoskeletons, fish scales and other organisms [2]. The main sources of cellulose are wood and to a lesser extent cotton [1], while chitin is typically sourced from waste from the marine food industry, such as crustacean shells (shrimp, crab and krill) [3]. While wood and cotton can be sustainable sources of cellulose, they are high-value materials with markets of their own. Crustacean-derived chitin also has disadvantages such as its seasonally and regionally limited supply and the environmentally unfriendly aggressive acid and alkaline treatment required for its purification and demineralisation [2]. Easily obtained, lower-value sources of cellulose exist in the form of agricultural by-products, such as sugarcane bagasse. Chitin can also be sourced from fungal biomass, which can be grown on other sugarcane by-products, such as blackstrap molasses [4, 5]. This study investigated paper-like materials produced from nanocellulose (NFC) sourced from sugarcane bagasse, fungal chitin sourced from *A. arbuscula* and *T. versicolor* mycelium fungal biomass and hybrid materials incorporating both NFC and fungal chitin in various ratios. Emphasis was on cost and environmental impact with only cheap agricultural by-products and natural fungal growth used to obtain the natural polymers utilised to produce the materials. Cellulose was bleached and ground to obtain NFC, while chitin was extracted from the mycelium fungal biomass using mild alkaline treatment, followed by vacuum filtration and hot-pressing to produce homogenous papers. The mechanical and surface properties of the papers were then analysed.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Allomyces arbuscula was obtained from the RMIT University fungal culture collection (Bundoora, Australia). The cultures were stored under oil on a nutrient agar slope, which was subcultured onto fresh sterile malt extract agar (Neogen, Michigan) plates and incubated inverted at 25°C in darkness for 7 d. *Trametes versicolor* was purchased from New Generation Mushroom Supplies (Melbourne, Australia). The sample was supplied as mycelium on wheat grain sealed in a plastic bag with a filter patch. This isolate was subcultured onto malt extract agar plates and incubated as above. Blackstrap molasses was purchased from Nortem Biotechnology (El Puerto de Santa Maria, Spain). Bleached sugarcane bagasse pulp was sourced from Lot No. 1201, Environment Pulp and Paper Co., Ltd, (Amphur Takli, Thailand). NaOH ($\geq 97.0\%$) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Deionised water was used for all experiments.

2.2 Fungal growth and biopolymer extraction

A. arbuscula and *T. versicolor* were selected for use in this study based on their high hyphal extensions rates and biomass yields [6]. Isolate cultures were cut into inoculum disks with a diameter of 7 mm and suspended in diluted blackstrap molasses (1 g/10 mL), a low cost and exceptional fungal nutrient [4]. Fungal growth over 14 d under ambient conditions (25°C) yielded floating biomass which could be easily separated from the diluted sugarcane molasses via vacuum filtration. Fungal biomass was washed three times and vacuum filtered before being blended for 5 min in 500 mL of water. The resulting suspension was heated to 85°C for 30 min, cooled to 25°C and centrifuged at 9000 rpm for 15 min at 18°C. The resultant residue was resuspended in a 1 M NaOH solution for 3 h at 65°C, before being again cooled and neutralised (pH 7) by repeated centrifugation and redispersion of the residue in water.

2.3 Preparation of nanocellulose

Nanocellulose (NFC) was produced by pre-soaking bleached sugarcane bagasse pulp material over-night in water. The material was blended for 5 min at 1000 rpm and then passed ten times through a disc mill (Granomat JP 150, Fuchs, Switzerland). The material was then dewatered over a cloth to a consistency of 3 wt%.

2.4 Hybrid paper production

Hybrid papers were produced from pre-determined quantities of NFC pulp and *A. arbuscula* or *T. versicolor* mycelium-derived polymer extracts in ratios of 1:1 and 75:25, which were blended in 300 mL of water for 5 min. The suspensions were vacuum filtered (VWR 125 mm qualitative filter paper 413, particle retention 5-13 μm), the filter paper removed and the filter cakes hotpressed at 120°C for 15 min under 20 kN of pressure. Neat nanocellulose mycelium-derived polymer extract papers were produced in the same way as reference samples.

2.5 Morphological and elemental analysis

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) elemental analysis mapping of each paper was performed using a Zeiss Supra 55 VP Scanning Electron Microscope with an Oxford X-Max^N 20 Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometer attached. An accelerating voltage of 30 kV was used. EDS mapping was completed using the AZtecEnergy EDS software.

2.6 Tensile properties

Dog bone shaped specimens (with dimensions based on type 1BA, EN ISO 527-2) with 5 mm parallel width and 75 mm overall length were cut using a Zwick ZCP 020 Manual Cutting Press (Zwick, Ulm, Germany). The thickness and mass of each specimen was then determined using a 0-25 mm digital outside micrometer (AnyiMeasuring, Guilin City, P.R. China) and a micro balance (Sartorius Cubis, Sartorius, Göttingen, Germany). Tensile tests were performed using an Instron universal test frame (Model 5969 Dual Column Universal Testing System, Instron, Darmstadt,

Germany) with a 1 kN load cell and a non-contact video extensometer (Gig ProE, iMETRIUM, Bristol, UK). The testing velocity was 1 mm/min with a gauge length of 25 mm. The elastic modulus (E) was analysed in the linear elastic region as a secant between strength values separated by 0.2 % strain. Additionally, the tensile strength (σ) was calculated using the maximum load the paper could withstand and the cross-sectional area of the specimen.

2.7 Surface properties

The advancing contact angles of polar (water) and non-polar (diiodo-methane) test liquids on the papers were determined using a Krüss DSA30 drop shape analyser. An initial contact angle measurement was recorded 0.5 s after dosing with double sessile drops (3 μ L drop of each test liquid), followed by 10 drops (0.2 μ L each) dosed and measured with 0.5 s delay between each drop. A total of 100 measurements at 10 individual sites were recorded and screened individually for each thin film to ensure that droplet profiles were well formed and level. Contact angle and surface free energy were calculated using the Owens, Wendt, Rabel and Kaelble (OWRK) method [7] in the Krüss Advance software (v 1.5.1).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical and mechanical properties

A. arbuscula mycelium-derived papers had higher ultimate tensile strengths (16 MPa) than papers derived from *T. versicolor* mycelium (0.9 MPa) (Table 1). Differences in the mechanical performance of the two species can most likely be attributed to significantly greater biomineralization of calcium, as CaCO_3 or oxalate [8, 9], in *T. versicolor* hyphae than in *A. arbuscula* (Fig. 1). Increased inorganic Ca salt content results in lower polymer content in the extract overall and coating of filaments, which affects the mechanical properties of the papers.

Figure 1. Energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) elemental composition maps for *A. arbuscula* and *T. versicolor* mycelium extract papers.

Tensile strength, elastic modulus and strain to failure of the samples were greatly improved through the incorporation of NFC in the papers to form mycelium polymer extract-NFC hybrid materials (Fig. 2). Improvements in mechanical performance scaled approximately linearly in line with the rule of mixtures based on the content of NFC and mycelium polymer extract in the papers. Mycelium extract-NFC hybrids (82-88 MPa) containing 50 wt% NFC exhibited tensile strengths up to 5 times higher than *A. arbuscula* mycelium polymer extract papers (16 MPa) and 98 times higher than *T. versicolor* mycelium polymer extract papers (0.9 MPa) (Table 1). Increasing NFC content in mycelium polymer extract-NFC hybrids to 75 wt% was associated with a corresponding increase in tensile strength to 105-110 MPa. Both *A. arbuscula* and *T. versicolor* exhibited similar tensile strength and elastic modulus for the same ratio of mycelium polymer extract to NFC (25 wt% mycelium polymer extract-75 wt% NFC or 50 wt% mycelium polymer extract-50 wt% NFC) despite the significant difference in the tensile strength of the two species (16 MPa compared to 0.9 MPa). *T. versicolor* mycelium polymer extract-NFC hybrids had similar strain to failure to pure cellulose papers (~3 %), while

hybrid materials produced from *A. arbuscula* mycelium polymer extract and NFC had a strain to failure of approximately 2%.

Figure 2. Tensile stress-strain curve for nanocellulose (NFC), mycelium only (*A. arbuscula* and *T. versicolor*) and mycelium-NFC (*A. arbuscula*-NFC and *T. versicolor*-NFC) hybrid papers.

Sample	E (GPa \pm SD)	σ_{UTS} (MPa \pm SD)	ϵ_f (% \pm SD)
Nanocellulose only (NFC)	12.6 \pm 0.3	161.8 \pm 6.0	3.4 \pm 0.6
25 wt% <i>T. versicolor</i> – 75 wt% NFC	10.8 \pm 0.3	110.1 \pm 13.8	3.2 \pm 1.0
50 wt% <i>T. versicolor</i> – 50 wt% NFC	6.9 \pm 0.2	88.3 \pm 3.5	3.0 \pm 0.3
<i>T. versicolor</i> only (mycelium)	0.7 \pm 0.01	0.9 \pm 0.1	0.1 \pm 0.01
25 wt% <i>A. arbuscula</i> – 75 wt% NFC	11.6 \pm 1.3	104.8 \pm 4.6	1.9 \pm 0.2
50 wt% <i>A. arbuscula</i> – 50 wt% NFC	8.9 \pm 0.4	81.6 \pm 9.4	2.1 \pm 0.4
<i>A. arbuscula</i> only (mycelium)	1.8 \pm 0.4	16.0 \pm 0.8	1.1 \pm 0.3

Table 1. Elastic modulus (E), ultimate tensile strength (σ_{UTS}) and strain to failure (ϵ_f) of nanocellulose (NFC), mycelium only (*A. arbuscula* and *T. versicolor*) and mycelium-NFC (*A. arbuscula*-NFC and *T. versicolor*-NFC) hybrid papers.

The mycelium polymer extract-NFC hybrid materials produced (*A. arbuscula*-NFC or *T. versicolor*-NFC) outperformed chitin-cellulose composite films prepared using ionic liquids, which had a tensile strength of 34.7 MPa and a strain to failure of 3.8% at a ratio of 1:7:6 [10]. Chitin-nanocellulose ratios of 1:3 were associated with tensile strengths of 8.2 MPa [11]. However, Butchosa et al. were able to produce composite materials from chitin nanocrystals, sourced from crab shells, and

bacterial nanocellulose, which is known for its high crystallinity, with tensile strengths of up to 155 MPa [12]. A similar trend of increasing tensile strength and elastic modulus with increasing nanocellulose content was also noted in their study.

3.2 Surface properties

Sugarcane bagasse derived NFC papers were hydrophilic with low water advancing contact angles of $\sim 38^\circ$ and free surface energy values of ~ 64 mN/m (Table 2). Conversely, *A. arbuscula* mycelium-derived papers had high water advancing contact angles and low free surface energy values ($\sim 106^\circ$ and ~ 28 mN/m, respectively) resulting from non-polar impurities responsible for the aroma of fungi, such as alcohols, acid derivatives and lipid residues in the fungal biomass [13]. *A. arbuscula* mycelium extract could be used to tune the wettability of the hybrid papers in a similar fashion to other natural polymers such as lignin, which is also associated with greater hydrophobicity [14]. Increasing *A. arbuscula* mycelium extract content was associated with increased hydrophobicity in the *A. arbuscula* mycelium extract-NFC hybrid papers (from $\sim 38^\circ$ for NFC to $\sim 50^\circ$ for mycelium extract-NFC hybrids containing 25 wt% *A. arbuscula* mycelium extract and $\sim 57^\circ$ for hybrids containing 50 wt% *A. arbuscula* mycelium extract).

Conversely, *T. versicolor* mycelium extract content had no significant influence on the wettability of the mycelium extract-NFC hybrid papers with no significant change in the water advancing contact angle and surface energy of *T. versicolor* mycelium extract-NFC hybrid papers comprising 25 wt% and 50 wt% *T. versicolor* mycelium extract (both $\sim 40^\circ$ and ~ 63 mN/m, respectively) compared to papers comprising only NFC ($\sim 38^\circ$ and ~ 64 mN/m, respectively). This was most likely due to the large quantities of hydrophilic Ca salts derived from the impure molasses growth medium and biomineralised in the *T. versicolor* mycelium [8]. Papers comprising only *T. versicolor* mycelium extract could not be tested as they did not support stable droplets.

Species	Advancing contact angle (θ_A)		Surface energy, γ (mN/m \pm SD)
	H ₂ O ($^\circ \pm$ SD)	CH ₂ I ₂ ($^\circ \pm$ SD)	
Nanocellulose only (NFC)	37.6 \pm 4.3	42.5 \pm 4.8	64.2 \pm 5.2
25 wt% <i>T. versicolor</i> – 75 wt% NFC	39.6 \pm 3.8	44.0 \pm 5.0	62.8 \pm 5.3
50 wt% <i>T. versicolor</i> – 50 wt% NFC	40.4 \pm 4.5	39.5 \pm 3.6	63.4 \pm 4.5
25 wt% <i>A. arbuscula</i> – 75 wt% NFC	50.1 \pm 3.5	60.7 \pm 6.0	52.1 \pm 6.6
50 wt% <i>A. arbuscula</i> – 50 wt% NFC	56.7 \pm 3.5	60.9 \pm 3.4	47.7 \pm 4.5
<i>A. arbuscula</i> only (mycelium)	106.3 \pm 6.9	60.6 \pm 7.6	28.3 \pm 4.6

Table 2. Advancing contact angle and surface energy of nanocellulose (NFC), mycelium (*A. arbuscula*) and mycelium-NFC (*A. arbuscula*-NFC and *T. versicolor*-NFC) hybrid papers. *T. versicolor* mycelium only papers could not be tested as they did not support stable droplets.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Paper-like materials with varying tensile and surface properties were produced from low-cost and easily obtained sources of cellulose and chitin. The agricultural by-product sugarcane bagasse was utilised as a source of cellulose, while *A. arbuscula* and *T. versicolor* fungal mycelium grown on the sugarcane by-product blackstrap molasses were treated to obtain a chitin-based polymer extract. Neat nanocellulose and mycelium polymer extract papers were produced which exhibited the highest and lowest tensile strengths and elastic moduli, respectively. Nanocellulose papers were highly hydrophilic, while papers derived from *A. arbuscula* mycelium polymer extract were hydrophobic. Hybrid papers incorporating 25 wt% and 50 wt% mycelium polymer extract with 75 wt% and 50 wt% nanocellulose, respectively, were also produced and yielded tensile strengths and elastic moduli strongly correlating with the nanocellulose content of the hybrid and the rule of mixtures. Fungal

species had no significant effect on the tensile strength of the hybrids, but did affect the surface properties of the papers with *T. versicolor* mycelium polymer extract content having no significant effect on the water advancing contact angle and free surface energy of the hybrid papers, while increasing *A. arbuscula* content increased the water advancing contact angle and decreased the surface energy of the papers. Overall, sugarcane bagasse and fungal mycelium provided low-cost and easily obtained sources of cellulose and chitin, which could be used to produce pure and hybrid papers with a range of tensile and surface properties, potentially suitable for applications including coatings, membranes and paper.

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